

Recommendation 19:

Open data & Open Government

Entrepreneurial and start-up culture

Using 'Open data & Open Government' to meet the business need 'Entrepreneurial and start-up culture'

Actual solutions and services:

Open data could help entrepreneurs to find necessary information about a specific region or economic or legislative conditions or they may be used as an input for the delivery of service.

There are a lot of initiatives which provide businesses with public sector information e.g.:

- EU Open Data Portal
- European Data portal
- Policy Compass Portal
- Public Contracts
- Open Coesione
- Visual OPML
- RES (Research and Education Space)
- 3cixty initiative of the Innovation Action Line Digital Cities
- Good Basic Data for Everyone" initiative in Denmark
- Publicspending.net

SWOT Analysis

Strengths

- **Enhanced government transparency**
- **Improved or new private products and services.**
- **Improved efficiency and effectiveness of government services.**
- **Technological innovation and economic growth by enabling third parties to develop new kinds of digital applications.**
- **New knowledge from combined data sources and patterns in large data volume.**
- **Acceleration of rate of scientific discovery by better access to data.**

Weaknesses

- Nowell defined standards
- Lack of data validation mechanisms regarding their veracity and completeness
- Collecting, 'cleaning', managing and disseminating data are typically labour- and/or cost-intensive processes.
- Additional processing is often needed by targeted end-users (analysis, apps, etc.).
- Little incentives to invest in the processing required to make data useful.

Opportunities

- **Promote birth of open data driven business ventures.**
- **Stimulate interagency benchmarking and learning.**
- **Generation of new business services around open data**

Threats

- Further advantage already privileged groups (e.g. a small elite of technical specialists or those who can afford to employ open data) -Increase the digital divide and social inequality, unless approached right.
- Concern that open data will be misinterpreted

Entrepreneurial and start-up culture:

An aspect that was highlighted by many informants is related to propelling a start-up culture in the EU and provide adequate incentives/training for the same. Some quotes expressing this need are: "Structured courses teaching how to become an entrepreneur", "Favourable fiscal regime for start-ups.", "Not enough motives for entrepreneurs."

Open data & open government:

Open government and open data are two highly intertwined concepts. Open Government stands for the governing doctrine which holds that citizens have the right to access the documents and proceedings of the government to allow for effective public scrutiny and oversight. Overall, Open Government is widely seen to be a key hallmark of contemporary democratic practice and is often linked to the passing of freedom of information legislation . In addition, the adoption of an open government approach enables the implementation of a government as a platform paradigm in which private entities are involved in the delivery of services of public interest.

*Open Data plays a crucial role allowing the implementation of open government practices. As a matter of fact it refers to the idea that some data should be freely available to everyone to use and republish as they wish without restrictions from copyright, patents and other mechanisms of control.**

* <http://open-dai.eu>

Wikipedia – Open Government, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_government

T. O'Reilly (2011) "Government as a platform" Innovations: Technology, Governance, Globalization. Volume 6, issue 1. MIT Press

Wikipedia – Open Data, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_data